

ASSESSMENT OF PRODUCT COMPETITIVENESS BASED ON QUALITY INDICATORS

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Competition is the driving force behind the development of society, the main tool for saving resources, improving the quality of goods and the standard of living of the population. The competitiveness of a product is a comprehensive characteristic of a product that determines its preference in the market compared to competing products both in terms of the degree of compliance with a specific social need and in terms of the costs of satisfying it. The competitiveness of products is measured by a set of indicators organized into four groups: qualitative, economic, organizational and commercial and socio-organizational indicators.

Qualitative (technical) parameters are strictly regulated. According to them it is possible to judge about the purpose of the goods, its belonging to a certain type of (class) of products. These are also characteristics that reflect technical and design solutions. Here include standards, norms, rules, regulations, legislative acts that define the limits of changes in technical parameters. And ergonomic indicators reflecting, how the product corresponds to the properties of the human body and its psyche (convenience of work, rate of fatigue, degree of connection between a person and a machine). Qualitative indicators of product competitiveness are the largest and well interpreted class of indicators.

An analysis of economic literature devoted to the assessment of competitiveness allows us to identify the following methodological approaches to solving the problem of comparative assessment of the competitiveness of retail chains with the aim of effectively managing it.

1. Assessment from the perspective of comparative advantage
2. Evaluation from the perspective of equilibrium theory
3. Assessment based on the theory of effective competition
4. Evaluation based on product quality
5. Assessment based on requirements profile
6. Assessment using SWOT analysis

7. Matrix method for assessing competitiveness
8. Difference method
9. Rank method
10. Rank method
11. DEA analysis method
12. “Standard” method (graphical method)

It is used to evaluate the effectiveness of systems of homogeneous objects that engage in the same types of activities and use the same resources. Such systems are chain stores. Each store is assessed by a set of parameters, which are divided into two categories: input - resources used by the store in its activities; weekends – the results of the store’s activities. The DEA method is based on finding relative operating efficiency as the ratio of the set of values of input parameters to the set of values of output parameters.

The compared indicators of product competitiveness are of great importance for a particular consumer. These include external, aesthetic, ergonomic, reliability indicators and others (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Qualitative indicators of product competitiveness

Based on a customer survey, we will analyze sample data according to consumer parameters on a five-point scale,

Table1

Scoring of knitted fabrics

№	Parameters	Samples			
		I	II	III	IV
1	Fibrous composition	5	5	5	5
2	Abrasion	5	5	4	4
3	Multiple washes	4	4	4	4
4	Pilling	2	3	2	2
5	Physical properties	4	4	4	4
6	Price	5	5	5	5
7	Sum of points	25	26	24	24

As can be seen from table. 1, sample “II” (26 points) is the best in quality. Sample “I” is somewhat inferior to it; “III” and “IV” are of the worst quality.

Thus, in order to calculate single indicators of competitiveness, sample “II” should be taken as a basis for comparison. Let's calculate single indicators of competitiveness for the i-th parameter using the following formula:

$$q_i = (P_i / P_{i_0}) \cdot 100\%, \quad (1)$$

where q_i is a single indicator of competitiveness according to the i-th parameter; P_i – the value of the i-th parameter for the analyzed product; P_{i_0} is the value of the i-th parameter for the sample taken as the basis of comparison.

Table2

The importance of competitiveness indicators

№	Parameters	Significance indicators	of Weight
1	Fibrous composition	5	0,21
2	Abrasion	4	0,17
3	Multiple washes	4	0,17
4	Pilling	2	0,08
5	Physical properties	4	0,17

6	Price	5	0,21
Σ	Sum of points	24	

The correspondence of a product to the need for it is characterized by group (or summary indices) indicators of competitiveness, which are calculated based on individual indicators. To do this, single indicators are combined taking into account the significance of each of them according to the formula:

$$I_{III} = \sum n_i = 1a_i \cdot q_i, (2),$$

where I_{pp} is a group indicator for consumer (technical) parameters; n is the number of parameters involved in the assessment; a -weight of the i -th parameter in the general set (weight coefficient); q -is a single indicator for the i -th technical parameter.

Table3
Single indicators of competitiveness

№	Parameters	Samples			
		I	II	III	IV
1	Fibrous composition	1,05	1,05	1,05	1,05
2	Abrasion	0,85	0,85	0,68	0,68
3	Multiple washes	0,51	0,68	0,68	0,68
4	Pilling	0,16	0,24	0,16	0,16
5	Physical properties	0,85	0,85	0,68	0,51
6	Price	1,05	1,05	1,05	1,05
Σ	Sum of points	4,47	4,72	4,3	4,13

In our example, for indicators characterizing the properties of “footer” knitted fabrics, the weight coefficients were determined as follows: the highest indicator for sample II is 4.72, the lowest indicator for sample IV is 4.13

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